

THE DISCRETE MODEL FOR COMPOSITES DM4C: MESOSCALE MODELING OF COMPOSITES VIA PHYSICS-BASED DISCRETE MATHEMATICAL MODELS OF FIBERS AND MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced composites have become integral to lightweight structural applications across aerospace, automotive, and renewable energy sectors. Accurately simulating their mechanical response remains a formidable challenge due to the intricate damage mechanisms governed by micro- and mesostructural features. This paper presents the Discrete Model for Composites (DM4C), a physics-based mesoscale simulation framework that explicitly represents fibers and matrix interactions. By modeling fibers as Timoshenko beams and employing vectorial traction-separation and frictional laws on facet surfaces derived from tetrahedral meshes, DM4C eliminates the need for artificial softening in compression or element erosion. The model is benchmarked against experimental data for IM7/977-3 and demonstrates strong predictive capability across various loading conditions, including longitudinal and transverse loading, as well as off-axis tension.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials offer high specific strength and stiffness and are increasingly applied in mission-critical structures [1,2]. Despite their advantages, predicting their failure remains challenging due to their anisotropy and heterogeneous damage evolution. Traditional continuum-based homogenized models often misrepresent the underlying physical mechanisms, relying heavily on empirical calibration and complex constitutive forms. These models struggle to reproduce essential failure modes like fiber kinking or matrix-dominated microcracking.

To overcome these challenges, the Discrete Model for Composites (DM4C) has been developed as a physics-driven, mesoscale simulation tool [3-5]. In this formulation, DM4C represents fibers explicitly using Timoshenko beam elements, while matrix behavior is captured by discrete constitutive laws defined on interfacial facets of a tetrahedral mesh. This facet-based formulation facilitates a direct simulation of fracture and delamination without relying on damage heuristics or eroding elements, enabling high-fidelity prediction of complex failure phenomena.

2 MESOSCALE MODELING FRAMEWORK

In DM4C, laminate generation starts from the mesoscale. As Figure 1 shows, fibers or bundles of fibers are modeled as Timoshenko beams, offering rotational degrees of freedom and capturing bending and shear deformations. Then, a Delaunay tetrahedralization is performed to connect the nodes of each beam. The result is the three-dimensional tet mesh shown in Figure 1b. After the tets are generated, Voronoi tessellation is used to identify surfaces, called “facets”, that are orthogonal to each edge of the tets. This way, each fiber is surrounded by a set of facets that are orthogonal to the edge

connecting the beam nodes. An orthonormal coordinate system can be defined on each facet. This enables the definition of normal and shear strains and normal and shear stresses through the constitutive laws. Hence, the constitutive behavior of the matrix connecting the fibers becomes vectorial instead of tensorial. This makes it easy compared to tensorial model to simulate phenomena such as cohesive failure or friction which are very important mechanisms for polymer composites which is one of the main advantages of the microplane model developed by Bažant and collaborators for the modelling of complex damage and fracture mechanisms in quasibrittle materials [6-10].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the DM4C framework for the description of fibers and matrix in fiber composites.

In a tetrahedral element, each facet divides the domain into four subregions, with each subregion containing one of the element's nodes. At every node:

- Three edges converge.
- Each edge is shared by two associated facets.

Within each subregion, a kinematic relation is defined. These local kinematic relations allow for the computation of strain vectors corresponding to the facets of the tetrahedral element.

The displacement field $u(x)$ inside each element is defined following the kinematic relation of nodes as follows:

$$u(x) = u_i + \theta_i \times (x - x_i) = A_i(x)Q_i \quad (1)$$

where:

$$A_i(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & x_3 - x_{3i} & x_{2i} - x_3 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & x_{3i} - x_3 & 0 & x_1 - x_{1i} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & x_2 - x_{2i} & x_{1i} - x_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The vector \mathbf{x} is the Cartesian coordinate inside the element, and the vector \mathbf{x}_i represents the coordinate of node i . The vector $Q_i^T = [u_i^T, \theta_i^T]$ is the ordered pair of the vector $u_i^T = [u_{1i}, u_{2i}, u_{3i}]$ and the vector $\theta_i^T = [\theta_{1i}, \theta_{2i}, \theta_{3i}]$ which are the translational and rotational degrees of freedom of node i .

Stress and strain vectors are defined at individual facets formulated from a Voronoi tessellation process in the tetrahedral mesh as described in the Lattice Discrete Particle Model (LDPM) [13, 14]. The strain components in each projected facet are computed leveraging the following equations:

$$\varepsilon_{Nk} = B_N^{jk} \mathbf{Q}_j - B_N^{ik} \mathbf{Q}_i \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{Mk} = B_M^{jk} \mathbf{Q}_j - B_M^{ik} \mathbf{Q}_i \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon_{Lk} = B_L^{jk} \mathbf{Q}_j - B_L^{ik} \mathbf{Q}_i \quad (5)$$

Once the stress vector for each facet is obtained through the constitutive relation, the nodal forces can be computed via the Principle of Virtual Work (PVW), which imposes that the total external work applied should be identical to the sum of internal work from all the facets. This leads to the following equation defining the internal energy associated with the facet k :

$$\delta W_k = \ell_k A_k \sigma_k^T \delta \varepsilon_k = \ell_k A_k (\sigma_{Nk} \delta \varepsilon_{Nk} + \sigma_{Mk} \delta \varepsilon_{Mk} + \sigma_{Lk} \delta \varepsilon_{Lk}) \quad (6)$$

where A_k is the area of a projected facet k .

By substituting the relations between strain components and the nodal degrees of freedom to Eq. (6), the nodal force vectors, F_{ik} and F_{jk} , for nodes i and j associated to the facet k can be computed as follows:

$$\delta W_k = F_{ik}^T \delta \mathbf{Q}_i + F_{jk}^T \delta \mathbf{Q}_j, \text{ where} \quad (7)$$

$$F_{ik}^T = -\ell_k A_k (\sigma_{Nk} B_N^{ik} + \sigma_{Mk} B_M^{ik} + \sigma_{Lk} B_L^{ik}) \quad (8)$$

$$F_{jk}^T = \ell_k A_k (\sigma_{Nk} B_N^{jk} + \sigma_{Mk} B_M^{jk} + \sigma_{Lk} B_L^{jk}) \quad (9)$$

2.1 Fiber Constitutive Law

In DM4C, fibers, groups of fibers, and tows are explicitly represented as Timoshenko beam elements; therefore, the constitutive law is described in the integration points of a beam element.

The axial stresses are evaluated at the integration points in the cross-section of a beam element. In the elastic regime, the axial stress is linearly proportional to the axial strain as follows:

$$\sigma_f = E_f \varepsilon_f \quad (10)$$

where E_f is the parameter associated to the modulus of the fiber bundle and is calibrated to match the longitudinal modulus of a composite material.

When the axial stress reaches the strength limit σ_c it follows a linear softening as defined by the following equation:

$$\sigma_f(\delta) = \max \left[0, \sigma_c \left(1 - \frac{\delta - \delta_c}{\delta_f - \delta_c} \right) \right] \quad (11)$$

where δ is the elongation of a beam element, $\delta_c = \sigma_c L_0 / E_f$, with L_0 being the length of the beam element, is the elastic limit displacement which determines the initiation of the linear softening. Complete failure occurs when the elongation of the beam element becomes greater of $\delta_f = (2 G_f) / \sigma_c$ where G_f is the fracture energy of fibers. In such a case, the axial stress calculated via Eq. (11) becomes zero.

2.1 Matrix Constitutive Law

The constitutive behavior of the matrix is defined at the facet level via vectorial stress-strain relationships. The equations for the elastic and inelastic behaviors are described in the following sections.

Elastic Behavior

The elastic relation for each component of strain and stress vectors resembles the Hooke's law in one-dimension:

$$\sigma_N = E_0 \varepsilon_N \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_M = \alpha E_0 \varepsilon_M \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_L = \alpha E_0 \varepsilon_L \quad (14)$$

where E_0 is effective mesoscale normal modulus, and α is a shear-normal coupling parameter. E_0 and α are the DM4C-matrix properties defined at the facet level that are calibrated to match the macroscopic elastic properties of a composite material in the transverse direction which is dominated by the properties of the matrix.

Tensile failure

When a facet deforms under positive normal strain, fracturing behavior determines the softening of the stress components. This behavior is characterized with the effect strain, ε , and the effective stress, σ , as defined in the following equations:

$$\varepsilon = \sqrt{\varepsilon_N^2 + \alpha(\varepsilon_M^2 + \varepsilon_L^2)} \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma_N^2 + (\sigma_M^2 + \sigma_L^2)/\alpha} \quad (16)$$

The effective stress incrementally increases proportionally to the effective strain until it reaches the tensile boundary σ_{bt} . As expressed in Eq. (17), the tensile boundary σ_{bt} has an exponential relationship with the normal-shear ratio variable ω and the history-dependent maximum effective strain ε_{max} following the Macaulay's notion: $\langle x \rangle = \max(x, 0)$:

$$\sigma_{bt}(\varepsilon, \omega) = \sigma_0(\omega) \exp\left(-H_0(\omega) \frac{\langle \varepsilon_{max} - \varepsilon_0(\omega) \rangle}{\sigma_0(\omega)}\right) \quad (17)$$

The normal-shear ratio variable ω is computed as

$$\tan \omega = \frac{\varepsilon_N}{\sqrt{\alpha} \varepsilon_T} \quad (18)$$

where $\varepsilon_T = \sqrt{\varepsilon_M^2 + \varepsilon_L^2}$. This variable indicates the degree of interaction between shear and normal load in a facet.

In Eq. (17), $\sigma_0(\omega)$ represents the strength limit of the effective stress and expressed as:

$$\sigma_0(\omega) = \sigma_t \frac{-\sin(\omega) + \sqrt{\sin^2(\omega) + 4\alpha \cos^2(\omega)/r_{st}^2}}{2\alpha \cos^2(\omega)/r_{st}^2} \quad (19)$$

where $r_{st} = \sigma_s/\sigma_t$ is the ratio between the shear strength σ_s and the tensile strength σ_t . The elastic limit $\varepsilon_0(\omega)$ is obtained by $\sigma_0(\omega)/E_0$.

The rate of decay of the tensile boundary $H_0(\omega)$ is also dependent on ω and is defined as:

$$H_0(\omega) = H_t \left(\frac{2\omega}{\pi} \right)^{n_t} \quad (20)$$

where $H_t = 2E_0/(l_t/l - 1)$ and $l_t = 2E_0G_t/\sigma_t^2$. G_t is associated to the fracture energy of the matrix, and l is the edge length of the tetrahedron element related to the facet in the evaluation.

Frictional behavior

Facets with compressive normal stress exhibit frictional behavior which increases the shear strength. The effective shear stress:

$$\sigma_T = \sqrt{\sigma_M^2 + \sigma_i^2} \quad (21)$$

increases incrementally until it reaches the shear boundary σ_{bs} defined as follows:

$$\sigma_{bs} = \sigma_s + \alpha(\mu_0 - \mu_\infty)\sigma_{N0} - \alpha\mu_\infty\sigma_N - \alpha(\mu_0 - \mu_\infty)\sigma_{N0} \exp\left(\frac{\sigma_N}{\sigma_{N0}}\right) \quad (22)$$

where σ_s is the shear strength of a facet under pure shear loading condition, and σ_{N0} is the parameter related to the σ_N at which the initial friction coefficient μ_0 transitions to the asymptotic friction coefficient μ_∞ .

Property	Value
Fiber strength limit, σ_c , (MPa)	4850
Fiber fracture energy, G_f , (N/m)	65000
Normal modulus, E_0 , (MPa)	10570
Shear-normal coupling, α	0.25
Matrix tensile strength, σ_t , (MPa)	50.0
Matrix shear strength, σ_s , (MPa)	45.0
Tensile Characteristic Length, l_t , (mm)	5
Softening exponent, n_t	0.3
Initial friction coefficient, μ_0	0.36
Asymptotic friction coefficient, μ_∞	0.36
Transitional stress, σ_{N0} , (MPa)	500
Compressive yielding strength, σ_{c0} , (MPa)	500
Initial hardening modulus ratio, H_{c0}/E_0	0.5
Transitional strain ratio, $\varepsilon_{c1}/\varepsilon_{c0}$	10.0
Deviatoric strain threshold ratio, κ_{c1}	1.0
Deviatoric damage parameter, κ_{c2}	5.0

Table 1: DM4C parameters calibrated for IM7/977-3

3 CALIBRATION

The DM4C formulation was calibrated against experimental results on IM7/977-3 provided by Clay and Knoch [11]. The whole gauge area of the specimen for each test was modeled using DM4C framework. To resemble the boundary conditions of the experiments, the nodes at the bottom surface were fixed in both translational and rotational degrees of freedom, and the nodes at the top surface were fixed in lateral direction so that the axial displacement is only allowed as a loading condition.

For the modeling of the gauge region, circular "super fibers" with a diameter of 100 μm were generated and distributed in a rectangular cross-section reaching approximately 60% of fiber volume fraction. The resulting calibrated DM4C parameters are listed in Table 1.

4 RESULTS

In this section, a comparison study between the DM4C simulation results and experimental data is presented.

4.1 Longitudinal Tension

The nominal stress-strain response from the simulation is shown in fig. 2(a). As a calibration result, the longitudinal tensile strength from DM4C model is in good agreement with the experimental data.

Figure 2. Longitudinal tension: (a) stress-strain curve, (b) damage morphology predicted by DM4C

In the DM4C simulation, fiber failure is the dominant mode of failure leading to the load drop under the tensile load in longitudinal direction as shown in fig. 2(b).

4.2 Longitudinal Compression

It is well-known that imperfections in fiber alignment, introduced during the composite manufacturing process, create local regions of elevated shear stress. Under compressive loading conditions, these regions of high shear stress can rapidly approach the matrix yield strength, triggering local instabilities around the fibers. Consequently, this localized reduction in shear stiffness causes fiber buckling and the subsequent formation of fiber kink bands [12].

Within the DM4C framework, artificial softening of fiber beams under compression is not employed. Instead, the primary damage mechanism causing the load drop is the localized instability resulting from a combination of fiber alignment imperfections and matrix plastic deformation. Therefore, accurately modeling these alignment imperfections is critical for calibrating the compressive strength in the longitudinal direction. The mesoscale nature of the DM4C framework allows for an explicit representation of fiber waviness induced during manufacturing.

In this study, fiber imperfection is modeled as a sinusoidal wave $y = a \cos(\pi x/\lambda)$ following Kyriakides et al. [13]. The amplitude and the half wave-length are calibrated to match the longitudinal compressive strength of IM7/977-3. The calibrated parameters normalized by the super fiber diameter ($d = 100 \sim \mu\text{m}$) of a fiber are: $a/d = 0.2$ and $\lambda/d = 27$. The slope of the sinusoidal wave characterized by the resultant parameters stays in the slope range observed in Kyriakides et al. [13].

Figure 3(a) presents the nominal stress-strain response derived from the simulations. The results demonstrate that the longitudinal compressive strength predicted by the DM4C model aligns closely with the experimental observations.

Figure 3. Longitudinal compression: (a) stress-strain curve, (b) damage morphology predicted by DM4C, (c) close up of a kink band.

Figure 4. Transverse compression: comparison between experiments and DM4C simulations.

As illustrated in Fig. 3(b), fiber kink bands develop once the nominal stress surpasses the critical threshold. It is also important to highlight that the matrix surrounding the buckled fibers undergoes damage, further reducing local shear stiffness.

The angle of the primary kink band at the onset of load drop was measured, as depicted in Fig. 3(c). Literature indicates that kink band angles typically range between 20 and 35 degrees [14]. The kink band morphology predicted by the DM4C model closely matches this experimentally reported range.

4.3 Transverse Compression

For transverse compression loading, the nominal stress-strain response obtained from the simulation is presented in Fig. 4. The calibrated transverse compressive strength predicted by the DM4C model demonstrates good agreement with the experimental data.

Within the DM4C simulations, shear band formation emerges as the primary failure mode, leading to load drop under transverse compression. The applied boundary conditions simulate a clamped scenario, permitting only axial displacement.

Unconfined compression tests (UCT) are commonly utilized to study matrix cracking under transverse compression. Previous studies [15,16] report the crack plane angles under transverse compression to typically range between 50 and 60 degrees. Figure 5 illustrates the resultant crack plane angle as predicted by DM4C, which closely aligns with the experimentally observed range reported in the literature [15,16].

Figure 5. Transverse compression: damage morphology predicted by DM4C.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work presented an innovative discrete modeling framework designed to accurately capture the mechanical behavior of fiber-reinforced composites. Through detailed comparisons with experimental results, our mesoscale simulations demonstrate the significant advantages of explicitly modeling fibers and matrix constituents. This explicit representation ensures that material parameters within the constitutive laws possess clear physical interpretations, simplifying calibration to match both elastic and strength characteristics of advanced composite materials like IM7/977-3. Moreover, the mesoscale approach excels at simulating complex and critical damage phenomena, including matrix micro-cracking induced by local shear stresses and fiber kink band formation resulting from fiber buckling. This modeling capability opens exciting possibilities for predicting and understanding composite material behavior under diverse loading conditions with unprecedented accuracy.

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